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ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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The Kept Hopes

Beautifully named after kind and noble
ubiquitous smile that exemplifies splendor
demure and soft voice depict placid nature
charm that entices me out of thin air

Caught up allured head over heels
her pulchritude is as right as rain
honeyed eyes that have your head in the clouds
like a bird chirping in skyline

Should all of these have no extremity
'cause what we have is none to compare
you just blast out life to my dull periphery
and all folks can see it eye to eye

You kept me cheered out of my shell
taken aback all of a sudden
you caused my heart to beat in unusual
this can no longer be contained herein

Hope this is easier said than done
to perpetuate these unfathomable feelings
and make two hearts beat as one
that long to break free from lingering doubts

Hope the beat of love prevails
and strings find its way to each other
suture together the loving hearts
that yearn to slink away from its coffer

Hope it won't be written in the river
and just waft away in forgotten
like a red rose died out of wither
and candid feelings just got thrown down

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Hope you could envisage it vividly
the feelings that spell out your name
the gestures that speak out sincerity
and appreciate the things that best in me

Hope you could grant me the ways
to retract these feelings from the menace of pain
to fill your night sky a constellation of stars
and to finally be the one thru thick and thin